

MICROBE
the Microbiome
Biobanking (RI)
Enabler

1st MICROBE project newsletter *(December 2023)*

Dear colleagues, friends and innovators,

Today, we would like to introduce our EU Project, MICROBE, which has kicked off a few months ago and will run until the end of January 2027. MICROBE aims to lead European advancement in microbiome biobanking with expertise and innovation.

Project MICROBE is dedicated to advancing the field of microbiome biobanking by addressing preservation and isolation methodologies, as well as data management. While some medical sectors have begun biobanking (gut) microbiome samples, the broader scientific community still grapples with challenges in preserving these complex samples and managing vast associated data.

MICROBE aims to pioneer optimised preservation techniques that maintain the composition and functionality of the microbiome samples. Moreover, we strive to create a cohesive data infrastructure, promoting standardisation across diverse sectors.

Collaborating with notable European research infrastructures like BBMRI-ERIC, MIRRI-ERIC, ELIXIR, and EMBRC-ERIC, MICROBE's objectives encompass developing and validating innovative preservation methods, recommending best practices, providing training, and exploring viable business models.

Another important aspect is the intended creation of a “MICROBE Community” to provide the foundation for knowledge exchange and research collaboration. This aspect will be elaborated upon further below in the newsletter.

Our MICROBE Consortium invites you to take part and integrate via our MICROBE Community.

Funded by
the European Union

Expected MICROBE project results

- › validated protocols for preserving and propagating complex microbiome samples
- › novel isolates of members of key microbiomes from different domains
- › novel synthetic consortia reproducing key functionalities of selected ecosystems
- › customised data infrastructure tools for microbiome biobanking
- › guidelines for implementing standardised microbiome biobanking workflows in selected fields
- › guidelines for establishing ethical and legal framework conditions enabling microbiome biobanking
- › business models for implementing and exploiting novel microbiome-based technologies and resources
- › training and educational activities

MICROBE Consortium

The MICROBE consortium is a group of experts possessing a wide array of complementary capabilities pivotal for pioneering the functional establishment of microbiome biobanking research infrastructures. The consortium's robustness is anchored in the diverse and extensive skills each partner injects, honed through years of managing microbial resources across distinct ecosystems. Within the consortium, scientific entities are acknowledged leaders in microbiome research, boasting deep-seated knowledge of specific use-case microbiomes such as soil, plant/seed, marine, and human microbiomes, alongside ready access to the corresponding biological materials. Routine implementation of microbiome analysis by these scientific partners ensures that experimental protocols for both laboratory operations and microbiome data management are well-established. Partners like DSMZ, CABI, INRAE, MUG, and SU also function within biobanking/culture collection settings, offering insights into existing procedural workflows. This expertise, coupled with EMBL's preeminence in bioinformatics and biological data stewardship, position the consortium to deliver exhaustive technological frameworks for microbiome biobanking endeavours.

In our project, we aim to promote our young researchers, showcase their work and expertise, and highlight their motivation for working within the MICROBE Consortium. In this newsletter, we start with Dr. Sara Pipponzi who is working as a PostDoc within the coordinating team at the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH in Tulln, Austria.

Dr. Sara Pipponzi

My name is Sara Pipponzi, and I graduated as a biologist at the University of Bologna in Italy. I completed my PhD at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, where I worked on beneficial bacteria associated with plants, focussing on applications for plant growth promotion and plant defence. My PhD gave me the opportunity to investigate some of the numerous and fascinating functions that microorganisms can perform in the environment in which they live.

For this reason, I am enthusiastic about the opportunity to dive deeper into this topic through my involvement in the MICROBE project as a PostDoc at the Bioresources Unit of the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology. My main tasks in the project are the preservation of microbiomes from soil and seeds and the establishment of high-throughput assays for the assessment of their functionality *in vivo*. I am looking forward to collaborating with all the partners involved in the project to develop useful methodologies to advance this interesting research field and its applications.

Link to Sara's workspace video: <https://tinyurl.com/ym9aucs8>

MICROBE aims to set up a community of relevant experts outside our consortium. Experts in the field of

- › microbiome research
- › preservation of microbes
- › isolation of microbes
- › storage and re-use of microbes
- › human environments of microbiomes
- › soil environments of microbiomes
- › sea environments of microbiomes
- › marine environments of microbiomes
- › standardisation

We invite you to register to our MICROBE Community and actively work with us.

Follow us!

Visit our website and register to our MICROBE Community

MICROBE events and news

Here, we present MICROBE events and workshops as well as events related to the areas we are working in.

MICROBE online workshop - Nagoya for Beginners

11th December 2023, 10:00 - 12:00

Join MICROBE online workshop on Nagoya Protocol and EU Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) Compliance!

This event is essential for anyone working with biological materials from other countries. We'll cover what researchers need to know about the Nagoya Protocol and EU ABS regulation, with a focus on Germany's user checks and the consequences of non-compliance.

Don't miss this opportunity to hear from our expert, Ms. Melania Muñoz García from the German Nagoya Protocol Hub and Leibniz Institute-DSMZ, Germany.

Further information and registration on:

<https://microbe-nagoya.eventbrite.com>

MICROBE online workshop - Keystone taxa & Core microbiota

15th January 2024, 08:00 - 12:00

Join MICROBE online workshop on defining 'Keystone Taxa' and 'Core Microbiota'!

This workshop is a call to action for experts keen on establishing common definitions for crucial microbiota concepts. We'll delve into the complexities of microbiota, the need for mechanistic understanding, and the role of cultivation-based approaches. The goal is to shape a consensus for an opinion paper.

This is a unique opportunity to contribute to defining isolation and cultivation strategies and setting up synthetic communities. Your insights could pave the way for groundbreaking research in microbiota.

Further information and registration on:

<https://microbe-taxa.eventbrite.com>

MICROBE project details

Duration: 02/2023 – 01/2027

EU Funding: € 5,804,683,-

HE-GA-Nr.: 101094353

www.microbeproject.eu